

Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn

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Isohexacosane, chlorobutanol, stearyl alcohol, β -sitosterol, ϵ -sitosterol and palmitic acid have been isolated from the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn. The isolation of isohexacosane and chlorobutanol have been reported for the first time from natural source.

XANTHIUM *strumarium* Linn (Family: Compositae) is a medium size herb which grows throughout the hot parts of India. This plant is reputed for its extensive medicinal importance. The whole plant is used as diaphoretic, sedative, sudorific and considered useful in long standing malaria. The root of the plant is used as bitter tonic and in the treatment of cancer and strumous diseases, while the fruits as cooling, demulcent and given in small-pox¹.

Bhakuni *et al.*² reported the isolation of β -sitosterol, γ -sitosterol, ϵ -sitosterol and the component fatty acids, palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic from the fruits of *Xanthium strumarium*. They also isolated strumaride, sugars; tartaric, succinic, malic, fumaric acids; amino acids, proteins and inorganic salts from the same source. Tsukamoto *et al.*³ isolated β -sitosterol, stigmasterol or campesterol from the seeds of this plant. The other constituents isolated by different workers from the plant material were Xanthatin⁴, Xanthinin^{4,5}, Xanthumin⁶, Xanthanol and isoxanthanol⁷, 8-(Δ^3 -isopentenyl)-5 : 7 : 3' : 4'-tetra hydroxy flavone⁸, caffeic acid and cinarin⁹ and essential oil¹⁰.

The present communication reports the isolation of isohexacosane, chlorobutanol, stearyl alcohol, β -sitosterol, ϵ -sitosterol and palmitic acid from the leaves of Indian *X. strumarium*.

The petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the leaves of the plant *Xanthium strumarium* Linn after column chromatography yielded a hydrocarbon and the pasty mass. The hydrocarbon C₂₆H₅₄, m.p. 60-61° have been characterised as isohexacosane by spectral analysis. The pasty mass was saponified, the unsaponifiable material was extracted with ether, and subjected to steam distillation after removing the solvent, which gave a white compound (purified by sublimation) C₄H₉Cl₃O, m.p. 96.5-97° and have been characterised as chlorobutanol by comparison

of m.p., UV, IR spectra etc. The chlorine was also estimated¹¹ in the dry leaves of the plant and was found to be 1.16±0.05%. The material left after steam distillation, on column chromatography yielded four compounds A, B, C and D. The compound A, C₁₈H₃₆O, m.p. 59-60°, was identified as stearyl alcohol by its m.m.p., IR spectrum and preparation of *p*-nitro benzoate, m.p. 64-65°. The compound B, C₂₈H₅₀O, m.p. 134-35°, was found to be β -sitosterol by m.m.p., IR and NMR spectra and preparation of its acetate, m.p. 120-21°. The compound C, C₂₈H₅₀O, m.p. 144-45°, identified as ϵ -sitosterol by m.m.p., IR spectrum and preparation of its acetate, m.p. 126-27°. The compound D, m.p. 156-57° could not be identified. The saponified part yielded palmitic acid C₁₆H₃₂O₂, m.p. 61-62°, identified by m.m.p., IR spectrum and preparation of its derivatives.

Experimental

The finely powdered air dried leaves of the plant (2 kg) collected from Baraut locality were extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a soxhlet extractor. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over Brockman alumina (250 g, deactivated with 10% AcOH) with petroleum ether and its mixture with benzene with increasing polarity, the ratio of the latter was increased slowly.

Isohexacosane

The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fraction furnished white solid, crystallised from petroleum ether in white granules (1 g), m.p. 60-61°, (Found : C, 85.02; H, 14.87%; Calc. for C₂₆H₅₄, C, 85.24; H, 14.75%).

Chlorobutanol

The benzene eluent was concentrated to dryness and hydrolysed with 0.5N alcoholic KOH on a steam bath. The unsaponifiable material was extracted with ether and solvent was distilled off. The amorphous residue thus obtained on steam distillation gave a white compound, which was

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finally purified by sublimation, colourless needles (2.5 g), m.p. 96.5–97°; (Found : C, 26.93; H, 3.91; Cl, 59.77%; Calc. for $C_8H_7Cl_3O$, C, 27.04; H, 3.98; Cl, 59.94%). It was characterised as chlorobutanol (β : β : β -trichloro-tert. butyl alcohol) by direct comparison with an authentic sample, m.m.p., Co-TLC and Co-IR.

The material left after steam distillation was extracted with chloroform and rechromatographed over deactivated alumina with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) and benzene, which yielded four compounds A, B, C and D. The compounds B, C and D gave a positive test for plant sterols.

Stearyl alcohol (Compound A) :

The compound A was crystallised from EtOH in white leaflets (0.9 g), m.p. 59–60°; (Found : C, 79.76; H, 14.23%; Calc. for $C_{18}H_{38}O$, C, 80.0; H, 14.07%). It was identified as stearyl alcohol by m.m.p. and preparation of its *p*-nitro benzoate (by the *p*-Nitrobenzoyl chloride/Py method, crystallised from MeOH as colourless crystals), m.p. 64–65°.

β -Sitosterol (Compound B)

The compound B was crystallised from MeOH in colourless plates (235 mg), m.p. 134–35°; (Found : C, 83.86; H, 12.22%; Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$, C, 84.06; H, 12.08%). It was identified as β -sitosterol and the identity was confirmed by m.m.p., NMR spectrum and preparation of its acetate (by the Ac_2O /Py method, crystallised from MeOH as colourless flakes), m.p. 120–121°.

e-Sitosterol (Compound C)

The compound C was crystallised from EtOAc-Ether (1 : 1) in colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 144–145°; (Found : C, 83.90; H, 12.10%; Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$, C, 84.06; H, 12.08%); ν_{max} (Nujol) 3400–3250, 1060, 1050, 1020, 970, 836, 800 and 715 cm^{-1} . It was identified as *e*-sitosterol by m.m.p. and preparation of its acetate (by the Ac_2O /Py method, crystallised from MeOH : $CHCl_3$ (1 : 1) as colourless needles), m.p. 126–127°.

Compound D

The compound D, m.p. 156–157°, gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test but could not be identified owing to lack of experimental evidence.

Palmitic acid

The saponified part was worked up as usual. This on chromatography over alumina yielded palmitic acid, white crystals (EtOH) (1.5 g), m.p. 61–62°, (Found : C, 74.82; H, 12.64%; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$, C, 75.00; H, 12.50%). The identity of the compound was confirmed by m.m.p. and preparation of amide m.p. 105–106° and anilide m.p. 88–89° in the usual way.

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